

ALIGNED DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBRES IN THERMOPLASTIC MATRICES VIA EXTRUSION OF UD TAPE

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1 Introduction

In industry much out-of-specification unidirectional carbon fibre (CF) reinforced thermoplastic composite tape is produced, especially at the beginning and end of tape production, this tape is generally discarded. The volume fraction of this material is typically 5-10% either side of the target 55-60 vol.%. This 'waste' material is particularly attractive for our process, as the CF has already been wetted-out by the thermoplastic polymer. Whilst efforts have been made to form discontinuous aligned CF-filled composites from discrete components using extrusion or injection moulding, most research has concerned the addition of dry chopped CFs with thermoplastics with wetting *in situ*; it is consequently difficult to realise materials with volume fractions > 0.3. A central aim of the current work is to use shear-induced alignment to obtain a high degree of fibre alignment in the flow direction.

The interactions between fibre-wall, fibre-fibre, and fibre-polymer interactions determine the degree of alignment and fibre attrition in such discontinuous composites. Fibre-wall interactions in the extrusion die induce shear forces, which result fibre alignment in the surface layers, along the flow axis [1]. The injection moulding of short glass fibre reinforced polypropylene revealed a relationship between injection speed and fibre alignment in the centre region. At high injection speeds the fibres have been observed to align perpendicular to the flow direction while at low injection speeds the fibre tended to orientate with the flow direction [1,2]. Extruded material exhibits a similar behaviour at different flow rates [1]. Convergent flow is known to promote fibre alignment parallel to the flow direction while a divergent flow leads to a fibre alignment transverse to the flow direction [1]. Fibres with a high aspect ratio have a higher tendency to align parallel with the flow direction, as they do not

cause as many perturbations in the velocity field of the fluid, leading to fibre rotation [1]. It is also known that higher fibre content leads to enhanced fibre-fibre interaction and even to fibre accumulation. The fibre-fibre interaction as well as the fibre accumulation can decrease the fibre alignment [1]. This is contrary to a study that demonstrated injection moulded short glass fibre/PEEK composites to have improved fibre alignment at an increase of the fibre content from 11 wt% to 18 wt% [3]. However, a study on short carbon extrusion/compounded and injection moulded short fibre/PEEK composites showed a higher fibre misalignment at a fibre content of 68wt% than at a fibre content of 30 wt% [4]. This suggests that fibre-fibre interactions should not be neglected at higher fibre loadings. From these previous studies, fibre alignment in the direction of flow can be enhanced by having: i) high fibre aspect ratio, ii) sufficient fibre-wall interactions, and iii) convergent flow and an optimised fibre content.

To our knowledge there are no examples of using already wetted out CF as feedstock, the technique described here enables us to produce aligned discontinues CF reinforced specimens with CF contents of ~ 54 vol.%.

Unidirectional CF/polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite tape of high fibre content was fed into a twin-screw extruder. A shear-inducing die was affixed to the gate of the extruder to produce square section samples that could be stacked and compression moulded. We envisage that these dies can be designed to produce rectangular section composite tape of high volume fraction aligned discontinuous CF-filled thermoplastic. This material can then be used for production of double curvature parts.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Feedstock Material

High volume fraction, unidirectional AS4 (un-sized) CF reinforced PEEK composite tape was used as feed-stock. This tape was produced using a batch-continuous line, described in detail elsewhere [5]. Composite tape was chopped into lengths of 15 cm and fed directly into the extruder. The action of the screws drew into the material.

2.2 Extrusion Parameters and Die Design

A co-rotating twin screw extruder, DSM XPlore 15 Micro Compounder Model 2005 (DSM, The Netherlands) was used in this work and fitted with a specially designed exit die (detailed below) to enable the production of discontinuous aligned CF filled PEEK that could undergo further compression moulding for production of larger samples. This extruder has an adjustable screw/cavity height as well as six heating zones which can be controlled separately up to 450 °C, allowing investigation into the influence of screw height and zonal heating on fibre attrition and alignment.

Initially a circular extrusion die as provided by the manufacturer was used. The internal diameter of the die is 3 mm, and the length of the flow channel is 6 mm. A two-part die (case-hardened steel) was designed that allowed for convergent flow, from a circular section gate (3 mm diameter) to square section (2.5 mm x 2.5 mm) exit, as shown in Figs. 1a-d. The transition region from circular to square cross-section was 5 mm (Fig. 1d). A relatively long flow path (20 mm) was chosen for the die to allow the material solidify under pressure during extrusion to reduce void content and induce fibre alignment via shear. Further, the cross-section of the square region of the die was designed to reduce cross section by 12% relative to the circular gate, this leads to a compression of the melt and was designed in an effort to suppress the effects of nitrogen gas entrainment and hence reduce void growth, observed when the short circular section die was used. The reduction of the cross-section also caused a convergent flow, which enhances the fibre alignment in flow direction [1]. The transition from the circular cross-section to the square cross-section was designed to be tangentially constant without steps. Steps between the circular cross-section and the

square cross-section would lead to fibre misalignment and fibre damage. In addition, steps could lead to stagnated areas, which can cause thermal degradation of the polymer melt due to an overheated standing material [6]. From literature, it is recommended that a length of 10 times the extrudate thickness to allow a relaxation of the polymer melt and prevent swelling effects. The term swelling effects refers to the phenomenon that the cross-section of an extrudate becomes larger after it exited the die. This effect is caused by a velocity relaxation of the polymer melt and a viscoelastic relaxation of the polymer molecules [6]. A long flow channel is also expected to promote a unidirectional alignment of the fibres due to shear effects. In addition, a long square cross-section enables investigation of the influence of flow length by taking samples from the inside of the extrusion die.

A parametric study was undertaken to determine the conditions to extrude material with the lowest void content, maximal fibre alignment and reduce the attrition of the fibre length. The effect of both screw speed and screw/cavity height on fibre attrition was investigated. Screw speed was varied between 5 and 40 RPM, and screw/cavity height varied between 1.2 and 4 mm to alter the shear forces. Two zonal heating regimes during compounding were investigated with: (i) the upper (near raw material feed) and mid zones set at 380 °C, with the zone nearest the gate at 400 °C, and (ii) with the upper zones were held at 235 °C, the middle at 275 °C and the zone nearest the gate held at 400 °C.

2.3 Method to investigate the fibre length in PEEK/carbon fibre extrudates

Acid digestion similar to a procedure described in ASTM D-3171 was used to extract the fibres from the matrix. The extruded samples (~0.15 g) were placed in a 250 ml beaker and 25 ml concentrated (95%) sulphuric acid was poured into the beaker. The sulphuric acid was heated on a heating plate (~150 °C) until it began to fume. Then 35 ml of 50% hydrogen peroxide was added. The hydrogen peroxide was added at a rate of 1 drop per 2 s and 1 drop per 1 s after 5 min. If the solution did not become clear, a further 5 ml hydrogen peroxide was added. Subsequently, the beaker was removed from the heating plate and 200 ml distilled water was

added to cool the solution down [7,8]. The cold solution was filtered in a Büchner funnel with cellulose ‘Whatman filter paper’ (Particle Retention Liquid 11µm, Air Flow rate 10.5 s/100 ml) and a vacuum flask. The wet filter and the fibres were placed in a petri-dish. Subsequently, the glass bowl was covered with aluminium foil, to minimise the loss of fibres during the drying in a vacuum oven. A needle was used to stamp holes [$d < 1$ mm] in the aluminium foil. The fibres were dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 1 hour.

The dried filters were patted to disperse a small amount of free carbon fibres into a glass bowl ($d = 20$ cm). Then the glass bowl was completely covered with another glass bowl and shaken to disperse the carbon fibres. Aluminium stubs with adhesion carbon tabs were pressed onto the surface of the glass bowls. A ‘JEOL JSM5610LV’ scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to assess the length of the fibres. Image analysis software, ‘ImageJ 1.6.0_20’ was used to analyse the microscope images. For each sample four pictures were taken from different regions per stub. For all length analysis 200 randomly selected fibres were measured in each sample. Alternatively, dried filters were patted to disperse carbon fibres on to microscopic slides. This microscopic slide was covered by a second microscopic slide. A polymer film (Parafilm “M”, Pechinery Plastic Packaging) was placed between the microscopic slides along the edges. The microscopic slides and the polymer film were heated to 80°C. The polymer melted and formed a stable joint between the microscopic slides. An ‘Olympus TGH MTV-3’ optical microscope connected to a ‘Imagine Micro Publisher 5. RTV’ video camera was used to take images of the fibres between the microscopic slides. The SEM as well as the optical microscope was suitable to investigate the fibre length. The SEM is more suitable for a large number of samples because several samples can be placed in the SEM, which reduced the set-up time. The optical microscope is more suitable for a small number of samples because only one sample can be placed on the mechanical stage.

The ‘Micromeritics-Accupyc 1330’ helium pycnometer was used to measure the absolute densities. Ten runs with five purges in each run were conducted for every sample. The purge fill pressure and the run fill pressure were set to 19.5 psi. The

arithmetic mean was regarded as the true value. The envelope densities of the samples were measured with the ‘Geopyc 1360’ powder pycnometer. Ten runs were conducted for every sample. The consolidation force was set to 28000 N. A chamber with a diameter of 12.7 mm was used. From the absolute density and the envelope density the porosity were calculated.

2.4 Investigation of fibre orientation

To quantify the fibre orientation in the extruded material, an approach similar to Yurgatis and Lee was followed [8,9]. First, samples of the extruded material were clamped into the block shown below and manually ground down to obtain a smooth supporting plane.

The ground samples were clamped in a metal clip and placed in a polyethylene container. A mixture of Epoxy Resin (Buehler EpoxiCure 20-8130-128) and Epoxy Hardener (Buehler Epoxy Cure 20-81-32-032) with a mixing ratio of 5:1 respectively was poured into the plastic container and left to harden for 12 h.

The hardened epoxy containing the sample was removed from the plastic container and polished in a ‘Buehler Metaserv Motopol 12’ polishing machine. Abrasive papers were used to obtain a high surface quality. The polished samples were investigated using an optical microscope ‘Olympus TGH MTV-3’ with a video camera ‘QImaging MicroPublisher 5 RTV’. The video camera was connected to a computer. Misaligned fibres appear ellipsoidal. The software ‘ImageJ 1.6.0_20’ was used to analyse the images. The length a_i of the major axis of the ellipse was measured and recorded. Equation (1) was used to calculate the angle θ_i between the normal of the surface plane and the fibre orientation. The plane cut angle φ_C was 90°. The diameter d_f of the AS4 carbon fibres was expected to be 7.1µm. 200 fibres were analysed for each angle distribution.

$$\varphi_i = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{d_f}{a_i} \right) - \varphi_C \quad (1)$$

2.5 Production of straightened specimens and stacked compression moulded composites

Despite a support guide after the die exit, the extruded material was not completely straight over its whole length; the curvature of a typical extrudate was measured to $1.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^{-1}$. A steel tool (machined, as shown in Fig 2) was used to straighten the extruded material in a post-processing step. This steel block has three slots; two of the slots have the same dimensions such as the nominal depth and width of the extruded material. The third slot has the same width like two extrudates and was used for compression moulding. Square-section extrudates were straightened using the confined tool (Fig. 2), and compression moulded at $360 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a force of 0.9 tons. The use of square sections, enable stacking to form larger composite specimens without fibre misalignment, using the mould shown in Fig. 3.

3 Results

The flow channel of the square section die acted to cool the material sufficiently and prevent the material relaxing hence extensive void formation, which was obvious using the short (6 mm long) circular die. The circular section die resulted in extensive void formation, predominantly towards the exterior of the sample, shown in Fig. 4. This void formation, due to relaxation effects and insufficient polymer cooling resulted in extensive fibre misalignment. Further, the circular sections could not be compression moulded as the material flowed causing further misalignment.

An optimised feeding rate of 1 cm min^{-1} was established to extrude continuously square cross sections. Too high a feeding rate resulted in expansion of the material at the die exit, which were highly porous, and extrudates of inconsistent cross-section. The optimised feeding rate allowed the melt to solidify in the extrusion die flow channel and exit the die with a square cross-section. An excessively low feeding rate led to a blocking of the extrusion die by solidified material. The rate of 1 cm min^{-1} resulted in the highest stability to the extrusion process. Frequently, however, the melt initially solidified within the die and blocked the flow channel. To prevent a solidification of the polymer melt within the extrusion die the temperature of the extrusion die was increased by wrapping the die in aluminium foil. The extrusion dies were also heated with a hot air gun. However, this led to an effect

similar to a high feeding rate. A solution was found by serendipitously; low density polyethylene (LDPE) 'cleaning polymer' can be used as initial lubricant. Prior to the extrusion of the PEEK/carbon fibre composite, the cleaning polymer was extruded. The extruder was cleaned with a brush and remaining material in the extrusion die was pulled out. Despite the cleaning, small amounts of the cleaning polymer remained in the machine and were found on the surface of the extruded PEEK/carbon fibre composite. After the initial extrudate of PEEK/carbon composite passed through the die, the extrusion was possible without further addition of other polymers.

By sampling fibres from different locations in the extruder, at the gate and exit, no correlation was observed between length and location for those in the already in the melt zone was found. The majority of the fibres were broken in the melt in the lower heating zone. Fibres in the upper and mid zones of the cavity, above the melt zone, were of lengths $> 1 \text{ mm}$. Longer fibres resulted from zonal heating (using condition (ii), described above). A screw speed of 30 RPM and screw/cavity height of 2 mm using these heating conditions resulted in greatest average fibre length in the extrudates, of $123 \pm 32 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, whereas fibres of length 96 ± 22 resulted when upper and mid zones were held at a temperature of $375 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The distribution of these fibre sizes for zonal heating conditions (i) and (ii – less exposure of the fibre in the polymer melt), are given in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively.

The improvement can be attributed to the shifting of the heating zones which shifted the melting zone closer to the exit of the extruder, which in turn reduces the residence time in the polymer melt leading to less fibre attrition. There was a weak trend to longer fibres with increasing screw/cavity height. The lower shear forces due to lower screw speeds did not lead to significantly longer fibres in the extruded material. The fibres remain a shorter time in the melt at higher screw speed. Turkovich and Erwin also observed that most fibre breakage occurs due to fibre-polymer interaction in the melt [10]. Thus at higher screw speeds, the fibres have less time to undergo breakage. The longest fibres ($123 \pm 20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) were found using a screw/cavity height of 2 mm and screw speed of 30 RPM.

The fibres have a high degree of alignment in the skin region, as shown in Figs. 7-8 (to a depth of ~ 0.5 mm from the outside of the extrudate towards the centre of the specimen cross-section); whereas the core region exhibited a spiral pattern with significant fibre misalignment (Fig. 7). We hypothesise that the spiral pattern originates from the screw rotation. This was anticipated due to shear forces causing fibre alignment in the surface layers and extensional flow in the centre region, which causes fibre misalignment [1]. The extrusion die had a strong effect on the porosity. The use of the square section die (Fig. 1) instead of the circular die reduced the porosity of the extrudate from ~ 20% to < 3%. The longer flow channel of the square section die also enabled the solidification of the polymer within the extrusion die. Thus the melt cools down under pressure, which reduces void growth [11].

In contrast to observations reported in literature [11], we did not find a correlation between fibre content and void content. The cooling under pressure seems to outweigh the influence of the fibre content.

The extruded square section samples could be stacked and fitted into a confined tool for compression moulding. Compression moulding did not alter the fibre alignment, as melt-flow was restricted (Fig. 9). The fibre alignment of the compression moulded material above is similar to the fibre alignment in the extruded material (Fig. 8). The alignment in the centre region is even slightly higher, which indicates variations in the extruded material. This proves that the extruded material with square cross-sections can undergo compression moulding without causing significant fibre misalignment. The porosity of the heated and compression moulded material was investigated qualitatively with polished cross-sections. Fig. 10 shows two extrudates that were heated together without the application of pressure, proving that reheating of the extruded material leads to massive void growth. Whereas application of compression leads to well consolidated samples Fig. 9.

4 Conclusions

A new processing route has been established to produce highly aligned, high fibre volume content CF reinforced thermoplastics by using already

wetted UD CF-thermoplastic material as feed stock for extrusion, where in situ fibre breakage occurs. Alignment is induced using exit dies, which allow the material to solidify under pressure.

The porosity of the extruded material was found to depend on the design of the extrusion die. A reduction of the porosity from over 20% to less than 3% was achieved by the use of extrusion dies with a long flow channel. Similar to injection moulding, dies with a long flow channel allow the melt to cool down under pressure and act to suppress void growth.

Subsequent compression moulding can be performed on the square section extrudate without loss of fibre alignment due to containing in the melt. This technique appears promising for the production of aligned discontinuous CF-PEEK tape and moulding of double curvature components.

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Fig. 1. Schematics of the steel die design: (A) Face fitting to the extruder die exit (circular entrance, middle); (B) Die exit (square); (C) Section of the die, showing half of the die, the flow channel and features for screwing the die to the extruder, and (D) detail view of the flow channel transition in section.

Fig. 2. Schematic and section of the mould used to straighten extruded short fibre composite square sections (2.5 x 2.5 mm²).

Fig. 3. Schematic and section of the mould used for compression moulding and consolidation of two extruded short fibre composite square sections for tensile test specimens (5 x 2.5 mm²).

Fig. 4. Cross-section of a sample extruded directly from the circular section exit gate of the extruder. Note the significant presence of voids towards the exterior/surface of the sample.

Fig. 5. Fibre length melting zone shifted (circular die)

Fig. 6. Fibre length melting zone not shifted (circular die)

Fig. 7. Cross-section of a sample extruded using the convergent flow die. Note the spiral formation, misalignment towards the core due to the influence of the screws, as opposed to the better-aligned CF in the skin region, which cooled under influence of shear.

Fig. 8. Representative optical micrograph of the skin region showing high degree of CF alignment.

Fig. 10. Image of uncompressed material showing extensive void formation.

Fig. 9. Representative optical micrograph of two square sections, fused together resulting from the compression moulding process; two spirals can be seen in the cores of the previously separate extrudates (left and right of the image)